

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ADHD - CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is among the most a neurodevelopmental pshycosomatic disorder, which affects millions of children and often persist in adulthood also. The core symptoms of ADHD are Inattention, hyperactivity, impulsivity. It is often associated with cooccurring disorders including disruptive, mood, anxiety and substance abuse. In Ayurveda, psychological and behavioral disorders are discussed in the chapter of unmada. So according to the clinical features of ADHD it can be correlated with Unmada. The present case was carried out in OPD&IPD kumarabhrithyam department, Sri adhishiva sadguru alisaheb shivaaryula ayurvedic medical college, Guntakal, A.P to evaluate the Ayurvedic treatment in management of ADHD. The given treatment was found to be effective in Management of ADHD.

KEYWORDS: ADHD, Ayurveda management, Unmada.

INTRODUCTION

ADHD is characterized by developmentally inappropriate levels of inattention, impulsivity and hyperactivity. It is a neurobiological disorder that affects 3-7% of school age children. However, it is now known that ADHD nearly always persists through adolescence and that many symptoms continue into adulthood also.

The symptom related criteria used to classify three primary subtypes of ADHD are adapted from DSM IV as follows.

- 1) ADHD predominantly inattentive (ADHD-I).
- 2) ADHD predominantly Hyperactive Impulsive (ADHD-HI).

3) ADHD Combined(ADHD-C).

Causes: More than 20 genetic studies have shown strong evidence that ADHD is inherited. Other causal factors such as low birth weight, prenatal maternal smoking and additional prenatal problems.^[1]

ADHD is diagnosed using criteria outlined in the DSM-5-TR (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of mental disorders, 5th edition, Text Revision).

According to *Ayurveda*, there is no direct correlation for ADHD, but based on its signs & symptoms it can be correlated with *unmada*. According to *charaka Acharya* causative factors of unmada are antagonistic, defective and impure food; insult to gods, teachers and *brahmanas*; mental shock due to fear or exhilaration and difficult postures are the cause of insanity. By these causative factors the *doshas* get vitiated in the person having small proportion of sattva guna and affect hrdaya, the seat of intellect. There from derange the mind of the person quickly. Perverted intellect, psychic agitation, restless eyes, impatience, incoherent speech and vacant mind are the general symptoms of the unmada. So due to loss of memory intellect and perception child lets the mind loose to wander here and there.^[2] Ayurvedic line of treatment has play key role in managing Neurodevelopmental pshycosomatic disorders like ADHD, Hence present case has taken to attempt how Ayurveda manage the ADHD.

CASE STUDY

A 6- year old male child with complaints of hyperactivity, irritability, inattentiveness, beats others and delayed speech had consulted our hospital with their parents. As per his parents information, the child was normal till 2 yrs of age, attained all gross motor mile stones as per chronological age and then after they observed delayed speech, behavioral disturbances in their child. He gradually developed hyper activity, can not sit for few minutes in one place, can not follow their commands, beats the other people with fear. Child had taken to so many hospitals and took treatment for this but they did not found much difference in his behavior. So they finally approached our hospital for further management.

Birth history

Term delivery with c- section(LSCS)

Birth weight- 2.5 kgs

Normal post natal history - birth cry present. No history of hospitalization after delivery.

Developmental history

Gross motor, fine motor development milestones achieved as per chronological age.

But there was delay in language and social development mile stones.

Family history

Non Consanguineous marriage, he has one elder sister (9 years), she is normal.

Personal history

Diet- mixed

Sleep – normal

Addiction- more mobile screen time

General Examination

Pallor, Hyperactive, inattentive

Anthropometry

Height:113 c.ms

Weight:18.5 kg

Head circumference:51 c.m

Cheat circumference:56 c.m

Mid arm circumference-14 c.m(both)

Mid thigh circumference-21 c.m(both)

Vitals

HR-101 bpm

Temp-normal

Systematic Examination

Examination of Cardio vascular system, Respiratory system, Gastro intestinal system, Musculo skeletal system shows no abnormality.

Central nervous system.

Higher mental functions-normal, conscious

Sensory system examination-normal

DSM V DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR ADHD^[3]

Inattentive type diagnostic criteria	
Displays poor listening skills	+
Loses or misplaces items needed to complete activities or tasks	+
Sidetracked by external or unimportant stimuli	+
Forgets daily activities	-
Diminished attention span	+
Lacks ability to complete schoolwork or to follow instructions	+
Fails to focus on details and/or makes thoughtless mistakes in school work	+
Hyperactive	
Squirms when seated or fidgets with feet/hands	+
Marked restlessness that is difficult to control	+
Appears to be driven by amotor or is often on the go	
Incapable of staying seated in class	+
Overly talkative	+
Impulsive	
Difficulty waiting turn	-
Interrupts or intrudes into conversations and activities of others	+
Impulsively blurts out answers before questions completed	+

As per DSM V ADHD criteria child was diagnosed as ADHD.

Scoring of clinical symptoms of ADHD

Hyperactivity, inattention, impulsivity were measured by obtaining a four point rating of DSM V criteria items. The scoring was given by never to very often as given below.

- Never -0
- Often -1
- Quite often -2
- Very often-3

ASTA STHANA PAREEKSHA

Nadi –Vata pittaja

Mala-prakrutha(normal)

Mutra-prakrutha

Jihwa-prakrutha

Sabdha-Prakrutha

Sparsa-sheetha

Drik -prakrutha

Akriti - alpa(lean)

TRESATMENT PLAN**Shamana Oushadhi**

1. Deepana & pachana – Agni tundi vati twice a day after food.
2. Swarnaprasana with Maha swarna brahma yoga 1 tablet with 5 ml of honey & 2 ml of ghee weakly once empty stomach.
3. Saraswatharistam 10 ml with 10 ml of water After food twice a day.
4. kalyanaka ghritham 10 ml with milk twice a day.

Sodhana Chikistha

1. Abhyangam with Ksheera bala tailam for 7 days.
2. Navara kizi (Sastika Sali pinda swedam) for 7 days.
3. Takra dhara for 14 days.
4. Shiropichu with Bramhi taila for 14 days.
5. Matravasti with Bramhi taila -30 ml.

Duration of study

The period of study is six months(3 consecutive sittings with interval of 2 months)

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Analysis was done before and after treatment based on clinical features of ADHD and scoring was given as per scales used for study.

Inattentive type diagnostic criteria	Before treatment	After treatment
Displays poor listening skills	3	2
Loses or misplaces items needed to complete activities or tasks	3	2
Sidetracked by external or unimportant stimuli	2	1
Forgets daily activities	0	0
Diminished attention span	4	3
Lacks ability to complete schoolwork or to follow instructions	4	3
Fails to focus on details and/or makes thoughtless mistakes in school work	4	3
Hyperactive		
Squirms when seated or fidgets with feet/hands	3	2
Marked restlessness that is difficult to control	2	2
Appears to be driven by a motor or is often on the go	3	2
Incapable of staying seated in class	3	2
Overly talkative	2	1
Impulsive		
Difficulty waiting turn	0	0
Interrupts or intrudes into conversations and activities of others	2	1
Impulsively blurts out answers before, questions completed	2	1

DISCUSSION

Probable mode of *samana ousadhi*

First of all, we need to increase the *jataragni*(appetite), so here *agnitungi vati* acts as *deepana*, *pachana*. *swarna prasana*, *saraswatharistam*, *Kalyanaka ghruthama* acts as *Medhya rasayan*as.

Probable mode of *abhyanga & Navarakizi*

Abhyanga with *ksheera bala* and *Navara kizi*(*Snigdha swedana*) acts as *brimhana*, *best vata prasamana*. which is suitable for children. It increases muscle tone, improves blood circulation also, it synergies between the Central nervous system composed of the spinal cord and the brain and the Peripheral nervous system. Beyond the support it provides to our cognitive capacities, increases dopamine and serotonin against a decrease in cortisol. Dopamine directly affects our memory, concentration and the ability to maintain motivation in regards to our tasks, especially creative or intellectual challenges.^[4]

Probable mode of *Takradhara*

The important areas of the brain, centre for judgment, centre for intellect, centre for speech etc are situated in frontal area, with *Takradhara* relaxation of the frontalis muscle occurs, tends to normalize the activities of the entire body, improve cerebral functions through increased cerebral blood flow, enhances concentration abilities and decrease in activity of sympathetic nervous system thus lowering the hyperactivity and impulsive behavior found in ADHD children. Thus relaxing mind and body.^[5]

Probable mode of *vasti*

Concept of mechanism of *vasti* can be interpreted by understanding the microanatomy of the gut. It reveals scattered, frequently solitary hormone producing cells of the stomach, intestines and pancreas. These are known as Gastro entero pancreatic endocrine system able to produce peptides and amines as active as hormones or as neurotransmitter. Gastro entero pancreatic system releases their secretions in response to nutrient stimulation from the circulation and lumen and has to potential to secrete into the circulation and lumen too. These specialized cells of gut are known as entero endocrine cells, enterocromaffin cells etc. as they exactly act like that of neurons of the brain, they are designated as paraneurons. The GEP endocrine cells are presumed to have receptor sites on their surface, adequate stimulation to which by Secretogogous reaction. When *Vasti dravyas* are passed through the GIT tract probably stimulate the cells and act as Secretogogous thus compensating neurological deficit and improving the functions.^[6]

Probable mode of siropichu

Bramhi taila siro pichu acts as *vata samana*, local effect is centered on cellular absorption of drugs through transdermal route. Systematically cellular absorption and circulation has possessions on Central nervous system. According to the modern medicine, local application like ointment permits through the stratum corneum into blood vessels. Similarly the oil on forehead can be absorbed and certainly extends to the brain cortex.^[6] We select *bramhitaila* here due to its *medhya* properties.

CONCLUSION

Now a days we observed number of ADHD cases increases rapidly. According to modern sciences treatment predominantly relies on prescribing stimulant medications and pshyosocial therapy. Stimulant drugs are used to treat ADHD has so many side effects like cardiovascular events etc. Therefore Ayurveda explains safe and effective therapies for various conditions, here we made an attempt to how Ayurveda give positive results on behavioral disorders like ADHD etc. We advised speech therapy also, they underwent speech therapy also through out the Ayurvedic treatment. After completing total therapy we observed positive changes in his behavior and his parents also happy for that.

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